

**A COMMENTARY ON RISK AND RESILIENCE IN THE HOSPITALITY, TOURISM, AVIATION
AND EVENTS INDUSTRY: RESPONSES TO COVID –19 AND LESSONS LEARNED**

Wendy Sealy
University of Chichester UK

Abstract

This paper will provide a commentary on the impacts of Covid-19 on the hospitality industry. It will examine the response of hotels in the USA and the Caribbean to Covid-19 and the implications. It will also look at the impacts on the aviation, events and restaurants sectors and the responses and challenges at the destination level. Finally, a synthesis of lessons learned from this disaster and best practices of risk mitigation across these sectors will conclude the discussion.

Keywords: COVID-19, Impacts, Hospitality Industry, Strategies of Risk and Resilience, Lockdowns

Introduction

Coronavirus has rocked the tourism and aviation industry with consequences never before experienced. Such events are nothing new to the tourism industry in that the industry has endured cyclones, earthquakes, wars, terrorist attacks, stock market crashes and a global financial crisis which led to long-term business implications and or disruption. Consequently, the industry has had to develop strategies of risk mitigation and resilience (Ritchie & Jiang, 2019). Coronavirus, likewise, is a global phenomenon which has incurred severe financial losses on the industry and has taken over a million lives. This paper examines the impacts of the corona virus on the events, hospitality, aviation, and tourism industry. It explores the sectorial responses and analyses the strategies of risk, disaster and resilience employed by hotels, airlines, restaurants, destinations, and event management companies due to the business disruption caused by the COVID –19 outbreak.

The response of world governments to the pandemic was to reduce the spread of the disease through mask wearing, social distancing, testing/quarantining, and lockdowns. The pandemic brought international travel to a standstill with airlines being grounded and international borders closed. Although these strategies did save lives, they triggered an economic crisis never experienced in history. At the time of writing, the financial consequences of the COVID-19 outbreak is still unknown and will undoubtedly accrue and accumulate for several years and in some ways may be unaccounted for since many of the losses will be intangible, unrecognisable, or unquantifiable. According to preliminary estimates, the UNWTO (2020) anticipate a loss of US\$30 to US\$50 billion in international tourism receipts. Global airlines stand to lose US\$113 billion in sales and Asia and the Pacific are expected to see a fall of 9% to 12% in tourists' arrivals. China's economy shrank 6.8 % in the first quarter of 2020 on a year-on-year basis. Eurozone economies shrank at a 14.8 % and in the United States, nearly 28 million persons filed new claims for unemployment benefits over the six-week period ending April 25, 2020. The U.S. economy shrank 4.8 % in the first quarter of 2020, and many analysts project it will

shrink at a rate of 25% or more by the second quarter. Estimates for other world regions are currently still uncertain (UNWTO, 2020). Cruise companies lost US\$750 million in revenue between January and March 2020 and the pandemic caused shares of Royal Caribbean, Carnival, and Norwegian to drop by 60 to 70%. Unfortunately, for USA cruise companies they are not eligible for the USA's government US\$500 billion aid package as many of them are not registered as American companies. Several cruise companies are registered outside the USA to take advantage of tax and other incentives offered by other countries.

The Hospitality Industry – Hotels

The major impact on hotels and resorts is business disruption with a consequential decline in revenue. Hotels have been closed or operating with vastly lower occupancies worldwide. Revenue forecast in the USA project a decline of around 50.6% (STR, 2020). During October 25-31, 2020 room demand in the USA fell by 1.3 million room nights from the prior week, leading to the USA's lowest average occupancy level of 44.4% since the week of June 14-20, 2020. The hotel industry in the USA supports nearly 8.3 million jobs from direct hotel operations, guest spending, indirect supply-chain and induced spending. Nearly 4 million hotel employees lost their jobs or were furloughed in the USA (AHLA, 2020). The CEO of Marriott International Hotels estimates that Marriott Hotels will lose around 75% in revenue as it has had to close the majority of its hotels worldwide. The Marriott corporation has placed employees on furlough, executive managers on 50% pay and the CEO and owner Bill Marriott have opted not to be paid for the rest of 2020 (Sorenson, 2020). Other hotel chains such as the Intercontinental group, have employed similar measures including cancelling all dividend payments to shareholders for 2020 while employing furloughs, staff reductions and flexible booking and re-booking policies to encourage future stays (AHLA, 2020). The underlying principle behind these moves is to conserve cash flow.

The main concern during this disruption is liquidity, but staff reductions alone will not compensate for the loss of room revenue due to the perishability of room nights. Unlike the retail sector where unsold goods can be stored and put for sale in the future, hotel room nights, once unsold, perish for good once the date has passed. Hotels also have fixed costs that would need to be met even though they may not be in operation. Empty hotels still need security and equipment will need to be maintained. A minimum staffing of reservation lines, distribution channels and public relations activity would be expected to continue and will incur costs.

In the USA, with a population of over 300 million people, domestic markets are anticipated to recover first and will provide a source of revenue for airlines and hotels. But recovery is likely to be slow and hotels will take time to build up their occupancies and revenue to pre-Covid-19 levels. It is anticipated that recovery will depend on consumer confidence that their health and safety will not be compromised. It is currently unclear how accommodation businesses will make sure that rooms are safe for newly arriving guests, or how individual COVID-19 cases occurring in accommodation establishments would be handled. Large hotel chains will also have to reconsider their global supply chains and distribution channels and the dependency structures these have created (Gössling, Scott & Hall, 2020). Hotel supply chains and distribution channels are very complex and fragmented structures. These include travel agents, tour operators, transport, food and material supply-lines, cleaning supplies, linens, etc. Although fragmented these networks are interdependent and failure on one part of the chain can have severe consequences on other parts of the network. Hotels who are overly dependent on tour operators and regional or international bookings will be particularly vulnerable to the decisions made by these other network entities. Tour operators in particular have significant autonomy and control over consumer travel choices and perceptions that can affect destinations

and hotels in tourism host countries. These issues are discussed in greater depth in relation to the Caribbean region below.

In the Caribbean, a similar response is painted with hotels closed and staff laid-off and placed on unemployment benefits in the islands where such benefits exist. Many hotels in this region are Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) which are less resilient to crises because they have lower levels of preparedness and rely more on government agencies (Todman-Lewis, 2017; Herbane, 2015). A matter of fact, Speakman and Sharpley (2012) iterate that SMEs assume that emergency planning is someone else's responsibility. SMEs often lack the necessary skills, resources, and knowledge to take appropriate action on disasters (Farooq & Aberideen, 2015). One of the primary challenges hotels in the Caribbean region is mitigating against a total shut down of the tourism industry due to the nonexistence of adequate domestic markets to fill the gaps left by international tourists. In these islands, hotels depend almost exclusively on international tourists which exacerbates the problem (Sealy & Mouatt, 2020). One major weakness in the marketing and management of hotels in the Caribbean is that they are overly dependent on inbound international tourists, airlines, and tour operator distribution channels for the majority of their business. Alarming, 90% of business coming to several hotels in the region is through USA and European tour operators (Sealy, 2018). Tour operators have significant, almost omni-potent, power over the behaviour, choices, and perceptions of the travelling public. They have the power to direct or redirect travellers to specific islands, destinations or hotels which makes small hotels and islands vulnerable to the corporate decisions of tour operators (Sealy, 2014). Although visitors pay for their vacations in advance, the majority and more powerful tour operators do not pay in advance and will only pay hotels 2-3 months after the client has departed the destination while some take longer to pay (Sealy & Seraphin, 2020). The European TUI and the Canadian Sunwing group of tour operators owe millions of US dollars to Caribbean hotels (Barbados Today, 2020). With most tour operators facing financial challenges due to refunds to travellers who had their vacations cancelled, the likely result for Caribbean hotels is escalating tour operator accounts receivable debt that will be difficult to recoup. The situation is exacerbated due to the fact that the tour operators will also have financial concerns to address. It's very likely that many of them will ask for extended credit or not pay at all. Tour operators are likely to require substantial discounts from hotels to relaunch themselves into the tourists' market and to prop up their own financial losses. Such discounts, if given, could lead to long-term brand damage. Barbados and other Caribbean hotels may find themselves having to recover from the financial losses incurred from the 'lockdown' caused by Covid-19 and then further financial losses incurred from heavy discounting given to the distribution channels. A significant portion of hotels are all-inclusive and therefore do not generate any cash flow at the local level since all vacation components including room, food & beverage and tours are paid for in advance to the tour operator, creating a zero-dollar tourism economy. 'Zero Dollar' tourism occurs when the destination experiences an increase in arrivals but a significant decrease in local expenditure because the money stays in the metropole where the tour operators are based (King, Dwyer & Prideaux, 2006). The Covid-19 crisis is further compounded by the fact that Thomas Cook's bankruptcy left many hotels out of pocket. According to reports, Thomas Cook owed £2.5 million to one hotel in Mexico (Taylor, 2020). Another hotel in Barbados depended on Thomas Cook for as much as 60% of their winter business (Myers, 2019). These events show the fragility of the islands and how unsustainable these tourism economies are. This model of tourism development does not allow destinations to generate the wealth needed at the local level to sustain economies. Unfortunately, many of these Caribbean islands are primarily, if not totally, dependent on tourism for their livelihoods (Beckles, 1990).

COVID-19 has brought home the reality that Caribbean hotels must evaluate their contracts with the distribution channels, suppliers, and all aspects of the tourism supply chain to ensure that the terms and conditions do not put them at a disadvantage when disaster strikes. The all-inclusive concept has also proven itself to be an unsustainable form of tourism and this urgently needs to be balanced with more community and village forms of tourism if small businesses and community traders are to survive the impacts of Covid-19. These outdated models of tourism development ensure that Caribbean islands remain dependent on the actions and decisions of metropolitan countries rather than on any effort of their own to self-determination despite achieving political independence.

Events – MICE

In the UK, the events industry is worth over £26 billion pounds and is a major source of income for many countries and a key destination marketing tool for attracting tourists (Getz & Page, 2020; Raj, Walters, & Rashid, 2017). As a result of this pandemic, governments have banned travel and gatherings for events resulting in the cancellation of events worldwide. Major sporting events, festivals, weddings, conferences, meetings, and educational seminars have all been cancelled or postponed with consequential substantial financial losses (Gössling, Scott & Hall, 2020).

The wedding industry has been particularly hard hit with widespread wedding venue closures and the cancellation of thousands of weddings including destination weddings. As social distancing continues to be employed, all forms of events in which large groups gather have been restricted. Major sports leagues across Europe and North America ended their seasons pre-maturely with the opening of others including the 2020 Summer Olympic Games postponed. In Barbados, the Crop Over Festival, a major source of income has been cancelled. Events that have gone ahead have done so with empty stadiums or auditoriums, depending on mainly television audiences and sponsorship for income. The combined economic impact is not yet known but will be in the hundreds of billions of pounds. This will also have repercussions for associated businesses such as hotels, venues, caterers, producers, decorators, transport companies – taxis, rail, coach, and air. The MICE and sports tourism industry is one of the hardest hit tourism sub-sectors.

The event sector has had to find new and innovative ways to engage with audiences through the application of technological communications software to produce events online (Seraphin, 2020). Zoom for instance, was downloaded 2.13 million times around the world on 23 March, 2020 (Neate, 2020) to facilitate 'virtual events. Seraphin notes that the virtual events market is worth \$18.6 billion and has provided the answer to the restrictions placed on travel and social distancing. Some events, such as the Miss USA 2020 Pageant, has been filmed in a studio and then streamed to audiences via a 'pay per view' platform on the internet and on television. In the future virtual events can be an alternative source of revenue and an adjunct to meeting in-person for those who are unable to travel. Several conferences, such as the Sustainable Tourism Conference, schedule for Kathmandu, Nepal, and the Graduate Employability Digital Conference, 2020 are now being delivered online. It is unlikely that virtual events will replace meeting in-person in the future. What is more likely is a move to hybrid events with events continuing to be delivered for a face-to-face audience with an adjunct virtual version from which revenue can be earned from registration fees. This is certainly the case with the 2021 Sustainable Tourism Conference, schedule for Kathmandu, Nepal. As Goldblatt (2011) stated, when humans meet it stimulates the human hormone 'pheromones', the feel-good hormone, which is activated when people come together face-to-face. Consequently, virtual events will grow in frequency and importance as they provide an additional revenue stream for event organisers, but they will be in addition to, and not a substitute for, live event experiences.

Restaurants

With social distancing being a key strategy to manage COVID-19 in many countries it is expected that restaurants, bars, pubs, and other food outlets will remain closed for several months. Restaurants typically have limited liquidity and small profit margins which means that 2-meter social distancing may not enable them to entertain the level of business that would make them financially viable. Where restaurants are allowed to stay open for take-away customers, this is an operational alternative, which requires fewer staff but would require a change in menus, business and operational models and additional hiring of new skills. A challenge for restaurants, cafes and coffee shops will be the implementation of new clearing and hygiene protocols and compliance with new hygiene regulations including mask wearing for staff and customers to instil confidence in customers that food will be safe. While the industry was still recovering from the first lockdown, restaurants, cafes, and catering service businesses were required to close again as new lockdowns were imposed by several European governments in the fall of 2020. These events highlight the need for a representative body to represent the needs of this sector not only at a governmental and parliamentary level but also to provide business advice and advise on health and safety practices that would allow these businesses to trade. Recently the website 'Bridebook' has taken the lead in forming the Association of British Wedding Businesses (ABWB) to represent the wedding sector in parliament. This has led to weddings continuing for up to 30 people during the November lockdown in the UK. Similar representation is needed for cafes, restaurants, pubs, and caterers as there is no reason why they should be closed since health and safety measures could easily be employed so that these businesses can continue to trade.

Airline industry

It is estimated that revenue losses in the airline sector will amount to US\$252 billion (IATA, 2020). Most airlines have less than three months liquidity and many are not expected to survive due to the transport restrictions (IATA, 2020). Carriers such as Delta and United Airlines, had less than two months of cash to cover expenses before the coronavirus hit (OECD, 2020). Airports are also suffering from financial losses estimated to be around US\$76.6 billion (Airports Council International, 2020). Asia Pacific and North American carriers are operating significantly fewer flights than they did in late-February 2020 and this pandemic has bought about the demise of the Boeing 747 and Airbus A380 giant aircrafts with major airlines across the globe making the decision to retire this equipment due to lack of market demand. Historically, the airline industry has recovered from the effects of multiple shocks, such as the financial crises, SARS, and the terrorism event of 9/11. This has reinforced the belief in the air transport industry's ability to rebound. The key issue is how can this industry reassure customers that air travel and airplanes will be as safe as before this pandemic. The ability or inability of airlines to rebound will affect other parts of the tourism system such as other forms of transport – bus, rail, airports, hotels, attractions, restaurants, conference centres, live experiences, and the entire hospitality industry. Even with an effective vaccine or other measures, airlines must clean up their act and put the health and safety of passengers and crew first. Major airlines like Etihad and Emirates have put cleaning protocols in place using sophisticated methods by embracing ultraviolet technology to eliminated dangerous bacteria from their planes and have launched public relations campaigns to reassure the public.

Job Market and Hospitality Education

The coronavirus pandemic has heralded the fastest reallocation of labour since World War II. Displaced workers have integrated into other industries or sectors that urgently need labour.

In the UK we have seen a boom in the health sector which has attracted workers from hospitality and customer service-oriented jobs. Airline cabin crew, whose customer service, health and safety, medical and first-aid training are transferable to the health and retail sectors, have migrated into the health sector (Barrero, Bloom & Davis). The post Covid-19 workplace requires a much higher skilled and confident workforce. The industry needs professionals who can bring expertise that would give a competitive advantage to the organisations that hire them. The transformation to virtual events has seen an influx of new jobs in virtual event management emerging on numerous job websites.

Table 1 Typical Jobs in Virtual Events Management as of November 2020

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual Event / Project Managers • Virtual Event / Hybrid Producers • Virtual Event / Hybrid Production Managers • Virtual Event / Hybrid Technicians • Virtual Event / Hybrid Designers • Virtual Event / Hybrid Client Services • Virtual Event / Hybrid Sales <p>Source: https://www.live-recruitment.co.uk/virtual-slash-hybrid-event-recruitment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual Hybrid Event Technician • Virtual Meeting Hosts • Virtual Event Champion (Volunteers) • Virtual Event Manager • Virtual Event Registration Coordinator • Virtual Sponsorship Executive • Virtual Event Digital Expert • Virtual Event Programme Manager • Content Producer (Virtual Event) • Virtual Wedding Coordinator • Virtual Event Sales Consultant <p>Source: Indeed.co.uk</p>
---	---

Maintaining a sustainable, engaged, skilled and experienced workforce in order to deliver quality event experiences will be crucial for events to continue. The post COVID -19 hospitality workforce must be committed to lifelong learning, increased levels of flexibility and adaptability to secure a career. To facilitate the trend to hybrid events workers must be tech savvy, digitally literate and outwardly mobile across several business sectors.

Several universities worldwide have shifted to online teaching; but the tourism and hospitality sectors, require their workforce to have a high level of interpersonal skills (Elshaer & Marzouk, 2019). This is where online learning presents a disadvantage to learners. Hospitality employers depend on the emotional labour of workers, including. face-to-face contact with the public; and the ability to produce a positive emotional state in another person and to activate the ‘pheromones’ which is central to the visitor experience and essential for business networking. Workers are also required to have a high level of emotional intelligence. However, these skills cannot be taught online. The above-mentioned skills continue to be increasingly valuable as they give workers the flexibility to move between different sectors following demand and capitalising on available resources and opportunities.

It is a graduate’s problem-solving ability that will help them as future managers to achieve a competitive advantage for their organizations and to adapt to the constantly changing

environments in which hospitality and tourism businesses now operate (Tan & Dwyer, 2014). Hospitality related curricula must move away from the strictly vocational and instead mould graduates who are technologically literate, innovators, critical thinkers, and problem solvers. It is important that hospitality students be instructed in decision-making tools that can facilitate best practice and innovative solutions to hotels, airlines, restaurants, events, and destination management.

Lessons Learned

Hospitality businesses can emerge from Covid-19 more resilient and with lessons to apply to the future. One of the biggest lessons is that disaster planning should be an integral part of strategic planning no matter how big or small the firm. Hospitality companies need to consider the risk associated with all aspects of business, particularly as it relates to external shocks. By using scenario-based planning businesses can determine how negative ecological, topographical, and biological (pandemics) events will affect all areas of their business and the ability of the business to cope. They need to consider how their operational and administrative policies and processes might contribute to their ability to deal with risk posed by other phenomenon and how this might affect the business. The low probability but high significant effects of crises threaten the existence of organizations (Weick, 1988) and thus requires attention.

This pandemic has shown how disaster may not only cause financial losses but also disruptions, such as staff shortages, business closure and the loss of valuable lifeline support services, including transportation, electricity, water, and communications such as internet and bandwidth and other technology failures (Kunkel, 2020). Scenario planning is key to being prepared for a range of different best case and worse case scenarios. Scenario planning allows businesses to better predict the multiple driving forces and possible outcomes and how the multiple variables may play out and to rehearse the future so that tactics and strategies could be devised in advance.

What we have learned so far is that liquidity planning is crucial to combat uncertainty. Planning for extended lengths of reduced revenue flow by conserving cash and considering a line of credit for the short term is a vital resilience strategy. Hospitality businesses must have a reserved cash flow set aside to cover salaries and fixed expenses for at least 6 months and beyond. Marriott hotels, due to its high levels of solvency, was able to buy the hotels that they manage in order to keep the owners solvent and to ensure the survival of this vital part of their supply chain. Hotels will need to realign and reduce costs by employing working capital, crisis management techniques and deferring capital expenditures. Innovation would be key in identifying areas where revenue could be earned even if this is from short-term, non-traditional sources. In the USA and the UK hotels and conference centres served as temporary hospital facilities or provided “work from home” environments for essential workers. Event venues may have to facilitate pop-up markets or warehouse facilities to those retail businesses that have been closed due to the pandemic in order to use up dead space; or they could be used as filming studios for events that are now pre-recorded due to the pandemic. How space and facilities will be used to create value will be tantamount to the recovery from Covid-19 until business can return to normal. This approach has been taken in the airline industry with airlines transporting cargo to maintain cashflow and Singapore airlines going as far as to offer tours of their parked aircrafts. Commercial airlines flew nearly 46,400 special cargo flights that transported 1.5 million tonnes of cargo, mostly medical equipment, to areas in need during the height of the pandemic to generate revenue (IATA, 2020).

Concerns for safety, security and health remains an important issue to address within the global travel and events industry. Businesses in tourism and related industries, will have to provide evidence of satisfactory hygiene, health, and safety measures to convince customers to come back again. No longer will the traveling public be satisfied with dirty airplanes or hotels. Accor hotel has joined forces with Veritas, the world leader in testing, inspection, and certification to develop a label called 'ALLSAFE' a hygiene certification, to support the return to business in the hospitality and catering sector. New certification outlets are important because they offer credibility (Elliott, 2013); recognition and contribute to the improvement of performances. Government must development policies and stricter regulations that should be followed by hospitality businesses (Foley, McGillivray, & McPherson, 2012). Ensuring that mask wearing, social distancing, sanitation and disinfection requirements are mandated is critical to consumer confidence in travelling once again. The digitalisation of hotel services and other technologies will gain relevance even more now with self-check in, concierge and room services as it will allow interactions between people and contact with surfaces to be reduced to the minimum possible. A re-training and reskilling of all hotel housekeepers on the use of chemicals is a way to ensure clearing attendants are working to keep everyone safe and surfaces germ-free.

At the destination level it is anticipated that traveller's need for safety and good health will be the decisive factor in their travel decision-making. Domestic tourism and short-haul trips will be the preferred mode of vacationing in the short-term in contrast to long haul travel to exotic places. We have already seen the formation of air-bridges between nearby countries in Europe that reciprocally acknowledge themselves as safe and where a quarantine is not necessary for residents of the airbridge countries. New and innovative packaging to attract travellers back to long-haul destinations will be the key to attracting visitors once again. We have seen Barbados investing in long-stay visitors by introducing a new travel regime called 'Work from at Home. This initiative gives visitors the option to live in Barbados for a year tax free. A major challenge for international destination marketers will be to consider how the flow of foreign exchange and employment could continue at the destination level if another shutdown of international travel were to occur. Could a destination be experienced through a virtual reality experience? Is virtual destination storytelling possible? Could digital destination festivals be something that the travelling public would pay for in lieu of travel to the destination? Could destinations and tour operators partner in the creation of a travel bubble? Could Covid-19 signal the end of the glitz and glamour of city tourism and will it bring a return to more sustainable, authentic types of tourism such as village and community tourism? The key challenges to a return to normal activity would be:

- Ensuring health and safety at the destination to restore traveller confidence, trust and to mitigate risks.
- Assessing and supporting all stakeholder and tourism businesses of large and small capacity to adapt and survive.
- Developing or sustaining a domestic tourism product until a safe return to international tourism can be achieved.
- Providing clear communication to international tourists to limit uncertainty and negative destination image.
- Developing systems for the measurement of travellers' needs, satisfaction and control of disease.
- Building an ongoing system of resilience for the future, the sustainable survival of communities and the micro and macro economies.
- Building on other industries to provide alternative sources of income and foreign exchange which will create less dependency on international tourism in small economies.

From this paper we have examine several initiatives that are lessons for the future. These are expressed in the below resilience framework which can inform future research.

Table 2 The Resilience Framework

Supply chain management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food, equipment & supplies - Travel Agents, tour operators & transport - GDS systems
Cash conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Divestment - Furlongs - Capital expenditure delays - Suspension of dividend payments - Insurance - Investments - Contract acquittal - Credit facilities - Vertical and horizontal integration
Government policy and support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concessions - Loans/grants - Furlongs - Geo-political issues - Country risk - Sponsorship - Regulations and legislation
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Malware - Software - Data protection - Virtual technologies
Media/Public relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Staff communications - External PR - Fake news - Timely and direct communications - Social media/Website communications - Social communications - SEO and meta search management - Guest, staff and community assistance - Designate spokesperson
Staff – Health and wellness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ergonomic risks - Safety, security of working at home - Accessibility to equipment, facilities, services - Medical support - Training and re-training - Health insurance - Mental health - Morale - Staff /skill shortages - Talent management

Destination management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brand management - Market recovery strategies - Innovative packaging - Technological applications - Paradigm shifts
Operational health/safety & hygiene management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hygiene and cleaning protocols - Communications to customers - Certification - Collaboration with manufacturers/Distributors & stakeholders - Technology & equipment - Staff training and re-training

Concluding Remarks

The sustainability of the events, hospitality and airline industry depends on the industries' willingness to experiment, learn new skills, explore new ideas, solutions, and opportunities, and respond to new customer needs and concerns. New ways of monetising business resources by creating new services and revenue streams will be critical in ensuring a lifeline for the future. Political and financial commitments are also key to ensure that these sectors can lead wider economic and social recovery on the back of the highly resilient nature of the sector and its ability to bounce back strongly. In places like the Caribbean, which is dominated by small hotels and where tourism businesses cater to opulent life-style jobs, there will need to be a shift in paradigm about the marketing of tourism products. While international corporate hotels tend to focus on expansion and growth, the attitudes of the Caribbean's industry professionals and entrepreneurs is totally different. In the Caribbean tourism marketing jobs usually involve the ostentatious consumption of international travel, wining and dining with the travel trade and attending red-carpet events (Pattulo, 2006). In the past, tourism operators have usually responded to different approaches, ideas, or concepts in tourism marketing with subtle but often aggressive rebuttal if these ideas threatened their lifestyles. Overall, much will depend on how governments handle this encounter with nature. It could become an economic crisis of global dimensions and a threat to globalisation, or it could be a moment when policymakers manage to rebuild trust and bring about sustainable change. It can also be a time for reflection, innovation and invention that can combat the virus and bring about a new and sustainable future.

References

- Airports Council International (2020). Retrieved from > <https://aci.aero/events/list/>. Accessed on November 20, 2020.
- AHLA (2020). 71% Of Hotels Won't Survive Another Six Months without Further Government COVID Relief. The American Hotel and Lodging Association. Retrieved from: <https://www.ahla.com/press-release/survey-71-hotels-wont-survive-another-six-months-without-further-government-covid>, Accessed on November 20 2020.
- Barbados Today (2020) Hotels want millions owed by tour operators (June 9, 2020). Retrieved from: <https://barbadostoday.bb/2020/06/09/hotels-want-millions-owed-by-tour-operators/#:~:text=%2D%20by%20Barbados%20Today%20June%209%2C%202020&text=One%20of%20the%20world's%20largest,time%20to%20pay%20the%20bills> Accessed on November 21, 2020

- Barrero, J. M., Bloom, N. & Davis, S.J. (2020). COVID-19 Is Also a Reallocation Shock. University of Chicago, Becker Friedman Institute for Economics Working Paper No. 2020-59.
- Beckles, H. (1990). *A history of Barbados: From Amerindian settlement to nation-state*. London: Cambridge University Press.
- Elliott, C. (2013). The impact of AACSB accreditation: A multiple case study of Canadian university business schools. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences / Revue Canadienne Des Sciences de L'administration*, 30 (3), 203–218.
- Elshaer, A. & Marzouk, A. M., (2019). Vocational skills training in higher tourism and hospitality education. *International Journal on Recent Trends in Business and Tourism (IJRTBT)*, 3 (3), 12-26.
- Foley, M., McGillivray, D. & McPherson, G. (2011). Events policy: the limits of democracy, *Journal of Policy Research in Tourism, Leisure and Events*, 3:3, 321-324.
- Farooq, W., & Abideen, Z. U. (2015). SMEs' Preparedness to face economic crisis: A proposed framework for Malaysian SMEs. *East West. Journal of Business and Social Studies*, 4, 66–79.
- Getz, D., & Page, S. J. (2020). *Events studies. Theory, research, and policy for planned events*. London: Routledge.
- Goldblatt, J. (2011). Prof. Goldblatt at HTMi on 'Event Trends'. Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XqBCh3cmS0s>, Accessed on November 20, 2020.
- Gossling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism, and global change: A rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*. doi:10.1080/09669582.2020.1758708.
- Herbane, B. (2015). Threat orientation in small and medium-sized enterprises: Understanding differences toward acute interruptions. *Disaster Prevention and Management*, 24 (5), 583–95.
- King, B., Dwyer, L., Prideaux, B. (2006). An evaluation of ethical business practices in Australia's China inbound tourism market. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 8, 127–142.
- Kunkel, M., (2020). *Lessons from a hurricane: Supply chain resilience in a disaster. An analysis of the US disaster response to hurricane Maria*. MPA Professional Paper in Partial Fulfilment of the Master of Public Affairs Degree Requirements. The Hubert H. Humphrey School of Public Affairs. The University of Minnesota Matthew Kunkel 9 September 2020.
- Myers, G.N, (2019). Caribbean tourism regroups after Thomas Cook demise. Retrieved From: <https://www.travelweekly.com/Caribbean-Travel/Insights/Caribbean-regroups-after-Thomas-Cook-demise>, Accessed on 19 November 2020.
- Neate, R. (2020). Zoom booms as demand for video-conferencing tech grows. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2020/mar/31/zoom-booms-as-demand-for-video-conferencing-tech-grows-in-coronavirus-outbreak>. Accessed on April 17, 2020.
- OECD (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on aviation Retrieved from: <http://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/covid-19-and-the-aviation-industry-impact-and-policy-responses-26d521c1/> Accessed on August 20, 2020.
- Pattullo, P. (2006). *Last resort: The cost of tourism in the Caribbean*. London: Wellington House.
- Ritchie, B, & Jiang Y. (2019). A review of research on tourism risk, crisis and disaster management: Launching the annals of tourism research curated collection on tourism risk, crisis and disaster management, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 79, 1-15.
- Raj, R., Walters, P., & Rashid, T. (2017). *Events management. Principles & Practice*. London: Sage.
- Sealy, W. (2014). *Tourism Intermediaries*. In S. Roberts, M. Best, & A. Cameron (Eds.), *Contemporary Caribbean tourism*. Kingston: Ian Randall Publishers.

- Sealy, W, (2018). 'From Colonialism to Transnationalism: The Neo-colonial Structure of Caribbean Tourism'. *Journal on Tourism and Sustainability*, 1 (2), June 2018.
- Sealy, W. & Mouatt, S, (2020). The Other Side of Paradise: The Cost of Tourism in the Caribbean. In Hermann, A. & Mouatt, S., (Eds) *Contemporary Issues in Heterodox Economics: Implications for Theory and Policy Action* (2020) Routledge.
- Sealy, W., & Seraphin, H. (2020). Hoteliers' Sources of Bargaining Power with British Tour Operators: A Barbados Case Study. *Journal on Tourism & Sustainability*, 3 (2),
- Seraphin, H. (2020). COVID-19: an opportunity to review existing grounded theories in event studies, *Journal of Convention & Event Tourism*, DOI: 10.1080/15470148.2020.1776657
- Sorenson, A. (2020). COVID-19. A message to Marriott International associates from President and CEO Arne Sorenson. Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SprFgoU6aO0>. Accessed pm 20 November.2020.
- Speakman, M., & Sharpley, R. (2012). A chaos theory perspective on destination crisis management: Evidence from Mexico. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 1(1), 67–77.
- STR (2020). US hotel occupancy continues to decline. Retrieved from: <https://www.hotelmanagement.net/operate/str-u-s-hotel-occupancy-continues-decline>. Accessed on November 20, 2020.
- Tan, J., & Dwyer, L (2014). Managing distribution channel conflict in the hotel industry. *International Journal of Marketing and Business Communication*, 3 (1), 9-19.
- Taylor, R. (2020). Thomas Cook owed hotels £338m when it collapsed, with the Civil Aviation Authority boss saying it's unsurprising they are angry. Retrieved from: <https://news.sky.com/story/thomas-cook-hotels-angry-over-millions-owed-in-collapse-with-one-due-2-5m-11819227>, Accessed on April 20, 2020.
- Todman - Lewis, Carrine, V. M. (2017). Strategies for crisis preparedness of tourist destinations" (2017). *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies*. 3327. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/3327>
- UNWTO (2020). International Travel could Fall 20-30%. Retrieved from: <https://www.unwto.org/news/international-tourism-arrivals-could-fall-in-2020>. Accessed 20 April 2020.
- Wang & Ritchie, B. (2010). A theoretical model for strategic crisis planning: factors influencing crisis planning in the hotel industry, *International Journal of Tourism Policy (IJTP)*, 3 (4) 2010
- Weick, K. (1988). Enacted sensemaking in crisis situations, *Journal of Management Studies*, 25 (4) 305-317.

Contributor: *Dr Wendy Sealy, Business School, University of Chichester UK*

Corresponding Author: *Dr Wendy Sealy. Email: W.Sealy@chi.ac.uk*